

Oxidative degradation of metronidazole by acidic potassium permanganate : A spectrophotometric kinetic study

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Manuscript received online 31 May 2017, accepted 08 June 2017

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of metronidazole (MTZ) by acidic KMnO_4 has been studied spectrophotometrically. The stoichiometry of reaction is found to be 5 : 2 ratio the main oxidation product were identified as 2-methyl-5-nitro-1-imidazole ethanol. The reaction was fractional order with respect to [MTZ] and $[\text{H}^+]$ and first order with respect to permanganate. The effect of added dielectric constant and ionic strength were studied. The reaction constant and overall thermodynamic activation parameters were calculated. The observed results have been explained through suitable mechanism and the relative rate law have been deduced on the basis of the experimental results and kinetic studies. Present work mainly deals with kinetics and oxidation of MTZ at different temperatures (288–303 K).

Keywords : Oxidation kinetics, metronidazole, temperature, acidic KMnO_4 .

Introduction

Pharmaceuticals are one of the major class of the pollutants as their concentration in the aquatic environment is low but due to continuous discharge and improper disposal cause potential risk for both human and animal life¹. Metronidazole is an antibiotic, anti-fungal drug² basically used for the treatment caused by anaerobic bacteria and protozoans^{3–6}. It is selected as a target compound for the study because of its highly solubility, low biodegradability and suspect as carcinogenic and mutagenic, induce DNA damage in human lymphocytes^{7–9}. Recently the concentrations of nitroimidazole antibiotics 0.1–90.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ have been detected in water¹⁰. Conventional treatment systems by the use of microorganisms, is not enough to effectively remove organic compound primarily due to its complex molecular structure. Thus, it can accumulate in aqueous environment causing adverse effects to human and ecological environment. Therefore, it is a basic need to explore the effectual methods to destruct

these contaminants from water system in appropriate and economically viable manner.

Potassium permanganate is one of the strong oxidizing agent^{11–13}, known due to its versatility, shows multiequivalent oxidation states commonly used for oxidation of inorganic and organic compounds and used as disinfectant^{14–16}. It is observed that permanganate is reduced to variable oxidation states in acidic, alkaline and neutral media. In acidic medium permanganate it exists in different form namely HMnO_4 , H_2MnO_4^+ , depends upon the behavior of the reductant^{17–22}. The oxidant is assigned both inner and outer sphere mechanism pathway in diverse redox reaction^{23,24}. It is easy to identify manganese intermediates when they have sufficiently longer life time^{25,26}. The main objective of the present work is to identify the effect of temperature on the kinetic and mechanistic route of the redox reaction as well as on the oxidation products.

Experimental

Materials and method :

All chemicals were employed in the present work from analytical reagent grade and triple distilled water was used throughout the experiment. MTZ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Mumbai), which later used without further purification for the preparation of stock solution. The solution potassium permanganate was prepared and standardized against oxalic acid. Perchloric acid was used to maintain the acidity of the reaction and the ionic strength was maintained constant by the addition of KCl, all the chemicals were obtained from E. Merck.

The oxidation of metronidazole by acidic KMnO_4 has been studied at four different temperatures by using CARY 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Varian). The kinetics were followed under first order condition where $[\text{MTZ}] > [\text{MnO}_4^-]$. The reaction begins by mixing the required quantity of previously thermostated solutions of metronidazole and permanganate which also contained fixed quantity of H^+ which maintained the acidity of the reaction. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically by recording absorbance of unreacted permanganate ion in the reaction mixture at the wavelength of 526 nm during the course of reaction. The applicability of Beer's law showed the evidence that the other species present in the reaction mixture, give negligible interference at the wavelength of 526 nm. The first order rate constant k_{obs} were obtained from the plots of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ vs time. The reactions were followed for more than three half lives of the reaction (Fig. 1). The rate constant was reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$ and are average at three independent kinetic runs.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The stoichiometry of overall reaction of MnO_4^- were excess over MTZ were kept in thermostatic water bath at constant temperature in the presence of H^+ for 72 h. The concentration of unreacted potassium permanganate was assayed periodically until it reached constant value. The result indicated that five mole of metronidazole was consumed by two moles of KMnO_4 . The oxidation reaction products were extracted with ether. The product of metronidazole has been identi-

Fig. 1. Spectral changes during the oxidation of metronidazole by MnO_4^- in aq. acidic medium at 298 K. Time interval = 0.5 min, $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{MTZ}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

fied as 2-methyl-5-nitro-1-imidazole ethanol (Scheme 1). The aldehyde was detected by conventional spot tests and 2,4-DNP derivative. Furthermore, the existence of aldehyde was confirmed by IR absorption bands at 1720 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching and at 2852 cm^{-1} for aldehydic $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching modes.

Accordingly, the following stoichiometric equation may be formulated as (A).

Results and discussion

The pseudo-first order reaction conditions were maintained in each kinetic run. The order of reaction determined from the slope of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log(\text{concentration})$ of substrate and medium by keeping all other reaction condition constant.

The order of the reaction with respect to $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ is found to be unity by varying the $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ in the range of $(0.5-5.0) \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, keeping all other conditions constant. The plot of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ vs time for different concentrations of permanganate were found to be straight lines indicates that rate constants were independent in the initial $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ stages in the presence of MTZ (Fig. 2) indicating pseudo-first order dependence on $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$.

Fig. 2. First order plots of oxidation of metronidazole by MnO_4^- in aqueous acidic medium. $[\text{MTZ}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-] \times 10^{-4} \text{ M} = 0.8, 1.0, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0$.

The substrate concentration was varied in the range $(1.0-10.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ at four different temperatures the result indicates that k_{obs} increased with increasing concentration of metronidazole. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{MTZ}]$ was linear with fractional slope (0.93) indicate fractional order with respect to substrate (Fig. 3). And the reaction order with respect to H^+ is found to be fractional by varying the concentration of H^+ in the range of $(0.5 \times 10^{-2}$ to $5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M})$. On plotting the graph between $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ at constant con-

Fig. 3. Plot of $4 + \log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{MTZ}]$ at four different temperatures 288 K, 293 K, 298 K, 303 K. Reaction conditions : $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{MTZ}] \times 10^{-3} \text{ M} = 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0$.

centration of substrate and permanganate, the value of slope is 0.46 indicating fractional order (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ at four different temperatures 288 K, 293 K, 298 K, 303 K. Reaction conditions: $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{MTZ}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+] \times 10^{-2} \text{ M} = 0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0$.

The effect of dielectric constant (D) in the rate of reaction has been studied by the variation of acetonitrile (CH_3CN) in the reaction medium and other reaction conditions were kept constant. The result revealed that the rate of reaction decreased with decreasing the value in the dielectric constant of the medium. The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying KCl concentrations from $(1 \times 10^{-2}$ to $10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M})$ at constant concentration of other reactants. It was found that on increasing ionic strength by KCl, no significant effect on the reaction rate was observed suggesting that the involvement of nonionic species at the rate-determining step.

Initially added Mn^{2+} did not have significant effect on the rate of reaction. The effect of fluoride ions on the rate of reaction was also investigated. Addition of sodium fluoride did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction. This means Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} are not the reactive species. The reaction mixture was prepared in an inert atmosphere i.e. nitrogen atmosphere to know the effect of dissolved oxygen on the rate of reaction. But, no significant difference in the results was observed. The reaction was also carried

out in order to confirm the contamination of carbonate in basic solutions. It was found that the externally added carbonate ions had no effect on the reaction rate. However, fresh solutions were used during the experiments.

From the above experimental results, the rate law may be written as :

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{d [\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{MTZ}]^{0.43}[\text{H}^+]^{0.93}$$

The effect of temperature on the rate was studied. The values of rate constant were found to be increased with increasing the temperature. The Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ was used to calculate activation energy related to these rate constants. With the help of activation energy, other thermodynamic parameters were calculated such as activation energy (E_a), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), Gibbs free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and Arrhenius factor (A).

Test for free radicals : To study the participation of free radicals was examined; the reaction mixture was added with known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger, which was then kept under an inert atmosphere for 2 h at room temperature. Upon dilution with methanol, precipitate was formed in the reaction mixture which indicated the involvement of free radicals in the reaction.

Reactive species of KMnO_4 :

The expected reactive species on permanganate oxidation in acidic medium is Mn^{III} , Mn^{IV} , Mn^{VII} . If the addition of complexing agent i.e. sodium fluoride will affect the rate of reaction i.e. by decreasing the rate the reactive species may be Mn^{II} , Mn^{IV} . In our experiments there is no effect of the ions on the rate of the reaction results that the permanganic acid is the most probable reactive active species in an aqueous acidic medium which elucidates the rate law to explained all the kinetic observation and other effects. The rate of reaction increased with increasing in $[\text{H}^+]$ due to the protonation of the oxidant resulting in the formation of more powerful oxidant i.e. permanganic acid. Depending upon the experimental results reac-

tion mechanism has been explored in which all the observed results will be considered. Increase in rate with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$. In prior equilibrium step H^+ first react with MnO_4^- form the reactive species HMnO_4 in first equilibrium step. In second step it reacts with MTZ form free radicals and Mn^{6+} in slow rate determining step. In fast step these free radical react and form Mn^{2+} satisfy the stoichiometric observation. The results interpreted in the form of Scheme 2. The stoichiometric and pH of reaction medium play their important roles.

Spectral evidence for the reaction shows in the proposed reaction scheme :

Spectral evidence for the complex formation between oxidant and substrate was obtained from UV-Visible spectra. As the reaction proceeded, color changed from violet Mn^{VII} to transparent at fixed concentration of H^+ . It is clear from Fig. 5 that the absorbance of MnO_4^- decreased at 526 nm, while at 603 and 460 nm increased. With increasing acid concentration of the medium, the rate of the reaction increased rapidly. The results imply that at first, the acid combines with permanganate giving rise to an acid-permanganate species $[\text{HMnO}_4]$. In the next step, $[\text{HMnO}_4]$ combined with MTZ to form an intermediate complex reduction product of Mn^{VII} i.e. Mn^{II} which is stable with no further reduction. The variable order with respect to MTZ probably resulted from the complex formation between the oxidant and MTZ, prior to the slow step.

Fig. 5. Spectral evidence from the complex formation between the oxidant and MTZ.

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According to reaction Scheme 1, considering the fact that five mole of metronidazole is oxidized by two mole of permanganate. The active species of permanganate in acidic medium can be deduced from the dependence of H^+ concentration in the reaction medium.

The order less than unity in $HClO_4$ suggest that the protonated form of permanganate is the active species of MnO_4^- in prior equilibrium which reacts with MTZ in second equilibrium step to form a complex C_2 that then decomposes in slow step to give product and Mn^{4+} .

Scheme 1

By considering (B-D) steps, the rate in term of decrease in concentration of potassium permanganate can be expressed as :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d [\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = k [\text{C}_2] \quad (1)$$

On the basis of equilibrium steps (B)-(D), eq. (2) can be obtained in the following forms :

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_1[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

With the help of eq. (2) we can write eq. (3) :

$$[\text{C}_2] = K_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}] \quad (3)$$

With the help of eqs. (1) and (3) we can write eq. (4) :

$$\text{Rate} = kK_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{MTZ}][\text{H}^+] \quad (4)$$

At any moment in the reaction, the total concentration of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T$ can be shown as :

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T = [\text{MnO}_4^-] + [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] \quad (5)$$

On substituting the value of $[\text{C}_1]$ and $[\text{C}_2]$ from eqs. (2) and (3) in eq. (5) we get eq. (6) :

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T = [\text{MnO}_4^-] + K_1[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}] \quad (6)$$

Above equation can be written as :

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = \frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}]} \quad (7)$$

Putting the value of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ from eq. (8) in eq. (5), we have eq. (9) :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{MnO}_4^-]_T [\text{MTZ}][\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}]} \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) is the rate law on the basis of which observed kinetic order with respect to each reactant of the reaction can very easily be explained.

Eq. (8) can be written as

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{MnO}_4^-]} = \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{MTZ}][\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}]} = k_{\text{obs}} \quad (9)$$

On reversing eq. (9), we have eq. (10)

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[\text{H}^+][\text{MTZ}]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[\text{MTZ}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) explored that if we plotting a graph between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{MTZ}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{H}^+]$, straight lines were found with positive intercepts at y-axes (Figs. 6 and 7). This proves the validity of rate law (8) and the proposed reaction scheme on the basis of which the rate law (8) has been derived. From the values of intercept and slope of the plots, k , K_1 , K_2 values at four different temperatures have been calculated. The effect ionic strength on the reaction rate has been based on the theory of Brönsted and Bjerrum, who suggest the reaction is due to the formation of an activated complex. According to this theory, the effect of ionic strength on the rate for a reaction is given by the following relationship :

$$\log k = \log k_0 + 1.02 Z_A Z_B \mu^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where, k and k_0 are the rate constants in the presence and absence of the added electrolyte, respectively. A plot of $\log k$ versus $I^{1/2}$ should be linear with a slope value of $1.02 Z_A Z_B$. If Z_A and Z_B have similar charges, the quantity $Z_A Z_B$ would be positive and the rate will increase with the ionic strength, with a positive value of slope, while, if both the ions have opposite charges, the value of $Z_A Z_B$ would be negative and the rate will decrease with increase in ionic strength, with a negative slope. In present work, negligible effect of ionic strength was found, consistent with involvement of neutral molecules in the reaction as shown in Scheme 1. The dependency of rate constant on the dielectric constant of medium can be explained by the following equation :

$$\log k = \log k_0 - \frac{Z_A Z_B e^2 N}{2.303(4\pi\epsilon)d_{AB}RT} \times \frac{1}{D} \quad (12)$$

where k_0 is the rate constant of the medium of infinite dielectric constant, Z_A and Z_B are the charges of reacting species, d_{AB} is the size of activated complex, T is

absolute temperature and D is dielectric constant of the medium. The effect of solvent composition on the rate of reaction is discussed in detail by Fröst and Pearson²⁷. The limiting case is zero angle approached between two dipoles or ion dipole system, Emis²⁸ has shown that plot of $\log k$ against $1/D$ gave a straight line, having a negative slope for a reaction between ions with same charged or dipole or between two dipoles. A positive slope obtained for oppositely charged ions or negative ion-dipole interactions. In the present work, when a graph is plotted between $\log k$ vs $1/D$, it gave a straight line with positive intercept. The former model agreed with the present observations. The value of d_{AB} for complex was calculated by the slope of straight line and found to be 1.18 Å. The validity of proposed mechanism was also confirmed by the moderate values of activation energy and other thermodynamic activation parameters. The higher positive values of free energy of activation and enthalpy of activation suggested that the transition state is highly solvated. Large negative value of entropy of activation revealed the formation of the compact activated complex with lesser degrees of freedom.

Multiple regression analysis : The relationship between three dependents i.e. pseudo-first order variable rate constant k and two independent variables i.e. $[MTZ]$ and $[H^+]$ in acidic medium to arrive at a conclusion whether the proposed reaction mechanism is well in accordance with our experimental kinetic data

Fig. 6. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[MTZ]$. Reaction conditions : $[MnO_4^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H^+] = 0.8 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[MTZ] \times 10^{-3} M = 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0$.

Fig. 7. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$, Reaction conditions : $[MnO_4^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[MTZ] = 4 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H^+] \times 10^{-2} M = 0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0$.

or not, we have taken the help of multivariate regression analysis using the computer package "STATGRAPHICS". On the basis of multivariate regression analysis, a correlation between the observed pseudo-first order rate constant (k) and concentrations of all the reactants, except MnO_4^- was determined at four different temperatures.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Temp. : } 288 \text{ K} & \quad k_1 = k [MTZ]^{0.934} [H^+]^{0.514} \\ \text{Temp. : } 293 \text{ K} & \quad k_1 = k [MTZ]^{0.933} [H^+]^{0.476} \\ \text{Temp. : } 298 \text{ K} & \quad k_1 = k [MTZ]^{0.933} [H^+]^{0.499} \\ \text{Temp. : } 303 \text{ K} & \quad k_1 = k [MTZ]^{0.933} [H^+]^{0.421} \end{aligned}$$

where, the value of k at 288 K = 0.393 s^{-1} , 293 K = 0.498 s^{-1} , 298 K = 0.832 s^{-1} , 303 K = 0.947 s^{-1} . The p -value in the ANOVA was found less than 0.01, hence, there must be a statistically significant relationship between the variables at the 99% confidence level which supported the validity of the rate law given in eq. (9). The suggested reaction in Scheme 1 is valid, as eq. (10) was used to calculate the rate constant based on the multiple regression analysis. The resemblance among all the three kinds of rates, i.e. observed (experimentally), calculated (from rate law) and theoretical (from regression analysis) results perfectly validate the rate law (expressed in eq. (8)) and the proposed mechanism.

Conclusion

In this paper, the oxidant, manganese(VII) exists in acidic media as alkali-permanganate species $[HMnO_4]$ which takes part in the chemical reaction. Rate of re-

action is increased with the temperature. The oxidation product of metronidazole is found to be 2-methyl-5-nitro-1-imidazole ethanol. The rate constant of the slowest step and other equilibrium constants involved in the reaction mechanism were evaluated and other thermodynamics parameters were calculated. The proposed mechanism is consistent with product, mechanistic and kinetic studies.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors is thankful to UGC, New Delhi for the award of Rajiv Gandhi National Fellowship as well as we would like to thank Govt. V. Y. T. P.G. Autonomous College, Durg, Chhattisgarh, for providing research facilities necessary for present work.

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